

MULTICAST CONFIGURATIONS & TUNING: QRS – Quick Reference Sheet

Configurations within Targeted Operational Protocols:

- **TOP-0** (1-way): (*similar* to Ghantous et al., (2020) OBC experiment*)
 - Perturbing the wind only for the parent
 - Downscaled child model errors via OBC (no upscale)
 - Multigrid Ensembles stored in directory MULTICAST/ENS/ENS9/BISCAY36-DG-1W/
- **TOP-1** (1-way): (*similar* to Ghantous et al., (2020) WINDxOBC experiment*)
 - Perturbing the wind for the parent & the child
 - Downscaled child model errors via OBC (no upscale)
 - Multigrid Ensembles stored in directory MULTICAST/ENS/ENS8/BISCAY36-DG-2W/
- **TOP-2** (2-way):
 - Perturbing the wind for the parent & the child
 - Upscaled/downscaled parent/child OBC model errors
 - Multigrid Ensembles stored in directory MULTICAST/ENS/ENS8/BISCAY36-DG-2W/

* Differences with respect to Ghantous et al., (2020)

- Short/medium vs. seasonal-range Ensembles/OBCs
- Online vs. offline 1-way coupling
- Malek's study is more coastal

Summary of multigrid analysis protocol options initially envisaged to address Target Operational Protocol-1:

Options in **bold** are currently planned in **T3** and **T4**

Option	Obs	Ensemble covariances	Impact on parent	Impact on child	Cross-grid influence
TOP-1.0	None		None	None	
TOP-1.1	Parent	Parent	Parent analysis	AGRIF 1-way	FALSE
TOP-1.2	Parent	Parent+Child under TOP-1	Parent analysis	AGRIF 1-way + cross-grid infl.	TRUE
TOP-1.3	Child	Child	None	Child analysis	FALSE
TOP-1.4	Child	Parent+Child under TOP-1	Cross-grid influence	Child analysis	TRUE
TOP-1.5	Parent+Child	Parent+Child under TOP-1	Parent analysis	AGRIF 1-way + Child analysis	TRUE

Summary of multigrid analysis protocol options initially envisaged to address Target Operational Protocol-2:

Options in **bold** are currently planned in **T3** and **T4**

Option	Obs	Ensemble covariances	Impact on parent	Impact on child	Cross-grid influence

TOP-2.0	None		None	None	
TOP-2.1	Parent	Parent	Parent analysis	AGRIF 2-way	FALSE
TOP-2.2	Parent	Parent+Child under TOP-2	Parent analysis	AGRIF 2-way + cross-grid infl.	TRUE
TOP-2.3	Child	Child	AGRIF 2-way	Child analysis	FALSE
TOP-2.4	Child	Parent+Child under TOP-2	AGRIF 2-way + cross-grid infl.	Child analysis	TRUE
TOP-2.5	Parent+Child	Parent+Child under TOP-2	AGRIF 2-way + Parent analysis	AGRIF 2-way + Child analysis	TRUE

Summary of the multigrid Target Operational Protocols (TOPs) currently planned for T3 and T4:

- For T3 all MG TOPs are of interest: TOP-0, TOP-1.0 and TOP-2.0
- For T4 only TOP-2.1 & TOP-2.2 and TOP-2.5.

The Ensembles:

- Ensembles are based on perturbations. Summary of essential elements of the **perturbation strategy**:
 - U_w,V_w wind perturbations
 - SPPT-AR1 (30% uncertainty, 2 degrees Gaussian truncated spatial structures, 3-days (de-)correlation temporal scales)
 - Exact same parent-child stochastic patterns (parent stochastic structures are projected onto the child domain, using the same seed number in their stochastic restarts per member and per season)
 - Different members are controlled by different spatial structures and seed numbers in the stochastic restarts.
- 30-day Ensemble simulations in two seasons including initial 10-day spin-up
- Daily model outputs (averaged)
- The last members of each sequence (x81, x51, x21) are used as **CONTROL** to generate pseudo-observations and run assimilation skill diagnostics
- NetCDF file format
- File name conventions:
 - parent: `???BISCAY36-DG-?W_1d_grid?_2017????-2017????.nc`
 - child: `1_???BISCAY108-DG-?W_1d_grid?_2017????-2017????.nc`
 - where
 - `1` denotes the first child in NEMO convention
 - `???` denotes the member number
 - `36` is only used for the parent BISCAY configuration and denotes the lower resolution 1/36°
 - `108` is only used for the child BISCAY configuration and denotes the higher resolution 1/108°
 - `?W` says whether the generating simulation was 1-way (i.e., TOP0 and TOP1) or 2-way (i.e., TOP2)
 - `grid?` – we use only the gridT to hold the state vector {ssh,T,S} (and optional ssh_ib); additional grids, not populated in the state vector, are obviously the gridU and gridV containing the 3D velocities and the wind stresses on the relevant Arakawa C-grids
 - `2017????` – the periods considered for the various 30-day runs are winter (20170112-20170210) and summer (20170601-20170630); the first 10 days of these periods are reserved for the Ensemble spin-up; for the assimilated experiments, those periods are further restricted to the last 20

days of the “free” periods, i.e., winter (20170122-20170210) and summer (20170611-20170630) following spin-up; the comparisons between experiments using MULTICAST metrics will be carried out on these 20-day periods.

- **Free (=unassimilated) members 500:**
 - **TOP0:** members 561-581 in directory MULTICAST/ENS/ENS9/BISCAY36-DG-1W/
 - **TOP1:** members 531-551 in directory MULTICAST/ENS/ENS8/BISCAY36-DG-1W/
 - **TOP2:** members 501-521 in directory MULTICAST/ENS/ENS8/BISCAY36-DG-2W/
- **Experiment 600+ members (subject to assimilation):**
 - The first 10 days are an exact copy of the 500 members (spin-up + prior), after which per-member assimilated fields are stored
 - **TOP1.5:** members 631-651 in directory MULTICAST/ENS/ENS8/BISCAY36-DG-1W/
 - **TOP2.5:** members 601-621 in directory MULTICAST/ENS/ENS8/BISCAY36-DG-2W/
- **And so on for further experiments (e.g., the 700+/800+ families of ensembles): replace 6xx above by 7xx/8xx, etc.**
 - **TOP1.1:** members 731-751 in directory MULTICAST/ENS/ENS8/BISCAY36-DG-1W/
 - **TOP2.1:** members 701-721 in directory MULTICAST/ENS/ENS8/BISCAY36-DG-2W/
 - **TOP1.2:** members 831-851 in directory MULTICAST/ENS/ENS8/BISCAY36-DG-1W/
 - **TOP2.2:** members 801-821 in directory MULTICAST/ENS/ENS8/BISCAY36-DG-2W/

Effect of assimilation on forecasting skill: error subspace processes targeted in T4 (but have consequences on the T3 protocol):

Highlighted in **yellow**: focus processes in MULTICAST.

Processes in response to wind errors	What we could see	What we see
(1) Barotropic processes (mostly on shelves)	Such processes are fast and we will not correct the wind, therefore we do not expect durable improvement in T4 (not beyond inertial time scales, which will not be resolved anyway by the daily Ensemble output).	Winter: barely detectable presence (SSH), only in the parent (Celtic Sea, etc.) . Seems somewhat addressed by assimilation within tiny amounts.
(2) Upwelling processes (onset, jet, weakening)	May or may not be present within the child domain depending on the wind regime.	Winter: no detectable presence (T).
(3) River plume displacements	Interesting but there is no major river nor plume or ROFI within the child perimeter. Rivers are in the East of the parent domain (Adour, Gironde, Loire, Vilaine), so the effect of assimilation onto forecasting skill will be seen only in the parent (not a multigrid topic, then).	Winter: significant presence (T), only in the parent . Seems well corrected by assimilation.
(4) Mid-shelf front displacements and vertical mixing processes	Interesting but within the child perimeter the shelf is narrow and does not show clear fronts – mid-shelf fronts are seen in the East (not a multigrid topic, then).	Winter: significant presence (T), only in the parent . Seems well corrected by assimilation.

	Periods are perhaps a bit short to see significant mixing at work.	
(5) Mesoscale processes	Interesting but the short periods (10-20 days) do not allow for the full development of Ensemble-wide statistical decorrelation of mesoscale structures. Only filament-like corrections of modest (but perhaps measurable) amplitude will be seen.	Winter: very weak presence (SSH, T, S). The small scales seem somewhat corrected by assimilation.
(6) Iberian Poleward Current (IPC) intrusion	Should appear in both domains as a Northward turning Eastward alongshore current carrying warmer waters. Usually stronger and more surface-intensified in winter. Some sensitivity to wind (in particular their meridional component, e.g. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pocean.2015.05.021).	We see mesoscale features as a result of meanders of the IPC stream. These features are believed to impact SST and hence IPC changes more as a statistical mean rather than as a coherent warm tongue.
(7) Seasonal thermocline build-up and erosion	Could be seen in the summer period.	Winter: no detectable presence (T).

- Which observations in CONTROL_OBS?
 - The fact that we use daily averages should keep the analysis on a slow attractor (tidal/inertial motions to be largely filtered out)
- Protocol adjustments:
 - The T4 time sequence (and therefore the T3 time sequence) are to be adjusted to this target
 - First guess: 10-day cycle, SST, SSH obs? Also T(z),S(z)?

IMPORTANT CONFIGURATION-RELEVANT NOTES (to sort out and perhaps incorporate in this sheet or in reports)

- **Bathymetry** – In TOP1, the default bathymetry NetCDF file of the BISCAY36 domain is used in the .prm file (same with the IBI36 subdomain bathymetry, used also in SCRUM/2), located at ECMWF directory “/ec/res4/scratch/hevv/MULTICAST/MISC/parent0_bathy_meter.nc” (created with nco commands from “BISCAY36_domain_cfg.nc”) and for TOP2 the bathymetry NetCDF file “parent_bathy_meter.nc” is used (created from “BISCAY36-DG_domain_cfg.nc”; pls. note, in TOP2, the AGRIF tool had slightly corrected the parent bathymetry wrt. the one used in 1-way i.e., TOP1)
 - How about the child bathymetry files? Are they modified by AGRIF as well?
 - The child domain calculated by the agrif tools is identical in 1-way and 2-way runs, and only the parent is slightly modified between 1-way and 2-way runs from the pre-processing agrif tools.
- The NetCDF **area mask files** used for the diagnostics in SDAP are the “1_child_areatabmask.v1.nc” and “parent0_areatabmask.v1.nc” (the child includes two areas dividing the domain in open-ocean and coastal/shelf-break with lesser than 2000m depth, and the parent includes four areas the two of them are the exact same previously mentioned for the child)
 - Are the area mask files the same for TOP1 and TOP2 diagnostics used by SDAP?
 - Yes, although this is an approximation for the parent domain in the 2-way TOP2 experiment, because there are (only minor) modifications in the parent coastline and bathymetry (and only in the common area with the child) brought by the AGRIF pre-processing tools. The -xgrid scumcat tool should give (slightly) more accurate results than using the mask areas.

- **NetCDF format for dxa** – Zero increment files for one member parent/child e.g., #601 are located in the ECMWF directory “ec/res4/scratch/hevv/DIRRUN_BISCAY36-DG-2WAY_test_asminc/assim_background_increments/” in a NetCDF NEMO-ready format. The format of the SDAP increments is nearly the same as the NEMO format (minor nco/cdo commands may be necessary to make those two formats identical). Zero increments for the parent/child NetCDF files can be used also as samples, containing all the proper information of the domain sizes, and can be overwritten with new SDAP increment calculations.
 - **Testing the sstrend metric on free members** – A recommendation from where we can download at least one case of a multi-day post-spin-up sequence:
 - Suggestion to download a few days after the 10-day spinup period from the members “500”, i.e.:
 - TOP1 free Ens. members #531-551, the total 20-day periods are: winter: 20170122-20170210 & summer: 20170611-20170630
 - TOP2 free Ens. members #501-521, the total 20-day periods are: winter: 20170122-20170210 & summer: 20170611-20170630
 - For the trend metric it is suggested to download just one-week e.g., winter: 20170122-20170128 & summer: 20170611-20170617
 - For the TOP2.x experiments, the trend metric and the other metrics as well have been tested for the 20-day period after correcting the Ensemble; depending on the TOP2.x experiment, there is an improvement wrt. the relevant free TOP2 experiment.
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